

2. Relevance of Knowledge Management in post Covid- 19 Era

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1. Introduction

No time can be such depressing as the time from March 2019 till date is. The rise of contagious COVID-19 has created an unprecedented crisis for the whole world. With its outbreak from Wuhan (China), more than 200 countries got infected having more than one crore confirmed cases and more than five lakh deaths. The virus has multiplied so quickly that Emerging Market and Developing Economies (EMDEs) like Brazil, India, Mexico, Russia and Turkey have to call upon strict lock-downs. In India, the first case of this lethal virus came on 30th January 2020. Soon, till 30th June 2020, it rose to 582147. 17322 people were threatened their lives till this date.

Figure 1: Trajectory of COVID-19 spread in India

Source: Based on data aggregated from MoHFW & State government health bulletins (India COVID-19 Tracker)

Extracted from Macroeconomic Report June 2020. Department of Economic Affairs, Economic Division, Government of India.

Note: Active Cases= Confirmed Cases – (Recovered Cases + Deaths), Average Daily Growth Rate in Active Cases (Last 5 Days) = Simply average of Daily Growth rates of active cases in last 5 days.

Figure 2: Death Rates due to COVID-19 in major countries

Source: 2019 Novel Coronavirus COVID-19 Data repository by John Hopkins CSSE.

Extracted from Macroeconomic Report June 2020. Department of Economic Affairs, Economic Division, Government of India.

Note: Death rate = COVID-19 deaths/Confirmed cases

Figure 3: Trade-off between flattening COVID-19 infection curve and steepening of recession curve

Source: Adapted from Gourinchas, P-O (2020), “Flattening the Pandemic and Recession Curves”, online manuscript.

Extracted from Macroeconomic Report June 2020. Department of Economic Affairs, Economic Division, Government of India.

To deal with the magnitude and virulence of COVID-19 Pandemic, “Lives vs livelihoods” debates started everywhere in the world. Thus, lock-down, restrictions on travelling and strict social distancing have been made vital to save the people. But these vital measures have also locked down the Livelihoods of people because non-essential economic activities have come to stand still.

Figure-4: Economic Implication of the Containment Measures taken during Pandemic

Source: Adapted from Estupinan, Xavier and Sharma, Mohit and Gupta, Sargam and Birla, “Import of COVID-19 Pandemic on Labour Supply and Gross Value Added in India (June 17, 2020)”. Extracted from Macroeconomic Report June 2020. Department of Economic Affairs, Economic Division, Government of India.

It is not so that economic activities are not affected. Production, Manufacturing and infrastructure sectors are working only on 40 percent of capacity even today. The service industry got the most fatal dent. Web-based services, software sector, education sectors and other such sectors where knowledge is an important ingredient for earning or livelihood are also heavily disappointed. A number of jobs are lost. Some of the growing companies are closed. Labour oriented sectors have become dumped.

But one sector that proved to be relevant in this COVID-19 era is Knowledge Management. The lock-downs and aloofness at home for months established that knowledge management has the capacity to deal strongly with such unexpected and unprecedented disasters. It not only boosted the moral of people but also it helped to keep the development cycle moving.

The present paper tries to drop-focus a light on the capacity of knowledge management in dealing with COVID-19 pandemic type situations so that the process of development and

progress can be kept moving. This paper discusses all the dimensions and approached with strategies and motivational factors that strongly established knowledge management as a unique method to deal disastrous situations.

2. Genesis and Concept of Knowledge Management

KM emerged as a scientific discipline in the earlier 1990s. It was initially supported solely by practitioners, when Skandia hired Leif Edinson of Sweden as the world's first Chief Knowledge Officer (CKO). Apprenticeship, discussion forums, corporate libraries, educational platforms and professional training programs are such fields that have best use of knowledge management. Use of computers in knowledge bases, expert systems, knowledge repositories, group decision support systems, intranets, and computer-supported cooperative work have enhanced the proliferation of KM. With the advent of Internet and Web-technology in recent past receiving of information has become super quick, easy and adequate. Computers and Internet created a new innovative field i.e., ICT, ICT has facilitated multiple tasks at on time, expansion of skills and knowledge, ranking among information, resources and policy implementation.

Further, "Knowledge Management can be defined as any structured activity that improves an organization's capacity to acquire, share and utilize knowledge that enhances its survival and success. The definition of knowledge management begs another definition of intellectual assets. Intellectual assets refer to anything valued without physical dimensions that is embedded in people or derived from processes, systems and the culture associated with an organization – brands, individual knowledge, licenses and forms of organizational knowledge (e.g. databases, Process know-how, and relationships).

3. Dimensions of Knowledge Management

Dimensions of knowledge management distinguishes between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge. Tacit knowledge represents internalized knowledge that an individual may not be consciously aware of, such as how he or she accomplishes particular tasks. At the opposite end, explicit knowledge represents knowledge that the individual holds consciously in mental focus, in a form that can easily be communicated to others. Early research suggested that a successful KM effort needs to convert internalized tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge to share it, and the same effort must permit individuals to internalize and make personally meaningful any codified knowledge retrieved from the KM effort. Subsequent research into KM suggested that a distinction between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge represented an

oversimplification and that the notion of explicit knowledge is self-contradictory. Specifically, for knowledge to be made explicit, it must be translated into information (i.e., symbols outside of our heads). Later on, Ikujiro Nonaka proposed a model (SECI for Socialization, Externalization, Combination, Internalization) which considers a spiraling knowledge process interaction between explicit knowledge and tacit knowledge.

Figure: -5 The Knowledge Spiral as described by Nonaka & Takeuchi

Source:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281892006_Influence_of_Relational_Psychological_Contract_and_Affective_Commitment_in_the_Intentions_of_Employee_to_Share_Tacit_Knowledge.

In this model, knowledge follows a cycle in which implicit knowledge is 'extracted' to become explicit knowledge, and explicit knowledge is 're-internalized' into implicit knowledge. A third proposed framework for categorizing the dimensions of knowledge distinguishes between the exploratory creation of "new knowledge" (i.e., innovation) vs. the transfer or exploitation of "established knowledge" within a group, organisation, or community. Collaborative environments such as communities of practice or the use of social computing tools can be used for both knowledge creation and transfer.

4. Approaches of KM is Post COVID-19 Era

Knowledge Management, as clear from the previous discussion, has the capacity to improve actual knowledge, managerial skills and to embed global position of an article and individual in a market place. But the main point that is in discussion is to apply the right approach of Knowledge Management. Following points can be put forth in support of knowledge management approaches –

- i. Knowledge management through an effective knowledge management system (KMS) helps to gather appropriate knowledge and to apply adequately that knowledge. Knowledge management system can create web-based application to distribute knowledge through different independent modules.
- ii. Knowledge management can play a vital role through ICT methods to research and to share innovative theories, basic documentation and latest technology trends. Email, social media, video conferencing, blogs, meeting apps and chat servers are KM tools that facilitate the interaction and involvement among the agreed parties. In context to seminar, research and survey, it can disseminate information to all phases all agreed and interested. Parties in phases.
- iii. Knowledge management has the power to strengthen the e-governance. Management, administration, responsiveness can be exercised & applied for better functioning and increased involvement.

5. Strategies and Motivations Provided by Knowledge Management

The concept of push and pull strategies may be applied in KMS. Push One strategy to KM involves actively managing knowledge. In such an instance, individuals strive to explicitly encode their knowledge into a shared knowledge repository, such as a database, as well as retrieving knowledge, they need that the repository are provided to other individuals. This is commonly known as the Codification approach to KM. Codification focuses on collecting and storing codified knowledge in previously designed electronic databases to make it accessible to the organisation. Codification can therefore refer to both tacit and explicit knowledge.

Pull to KM involves individuals making knowledge requests of experts associated with a particular subject on an ad hoc basis (pull strategy). In such an instance, expert individual(s) can provide their insights to the particular person or people needing this. This is commonly known as the Personalisation approach to KM. Personalization strategy aims at encouraging individuals to share their knowledge directly. Information technology plays a less important role, as it is only supposed to facilitate communication and knowledge sharing among members of an organisation. Other knowledge management strategies and instruments for organisation include:

- fostering a culture that encourages the sharing of information, based on the concept that knowledge is not irrevocable and should be shared and updated to remain relevant

- transferring tacit knowledge a map of knowledge repositories within an organization (accessible by all)
- Expert directories (to enable knowledge seeker to reach to the experts)
- Expert Systems (knowledge seeker responds to one or more specific questions to reach knowledge in a repository)
- Competence management (systematic evaluation and planning of competences of individual organisation members)
- Proximity & architecture (the physical situation of employees can be either conducive or obstructive to knowledge sharing)
- Collaborative technologies (groupware, etc.)
- Knowledge repositories (databases, bookmarking engines, etc.)
- Measuring and reporting intellectual capital (a way of making explicit knowledge for companies)
- Knowledge brokers (some organisational members take on responsibility for a specific "field" and act as first reference on whom to talk about a specific subject)
- Social software (wikis, social bookmarking, blogs, etc.)
- Inter-project knowledge transfer

The COVID-19 Pandemic era has forced everyone to be held up in the boundaries of their house world over. But, the process of growth and development cannot be hampered in any way. There were such professions that could not spare their selves even from the fears fo COVID virus. And, to fight bravely with an invisible enemy need to maintain knowledge development and knowledge sharing a continuous process. If knowledge sharing and development stops, the whole process of social and cultural development will come to a standstill. COVID-19 Pandemic has created a vibrant relevance and need of knowledge management in every walk of life.

6. Knowledge Management Technologies

Knowledge Management (KM) technology can be divided into the following general categories:

- a. **Groupware:** It is a techno-tool that initiate collaboration and sharing of various information.
- b. **Workflow:** It helps to represent creation, use and maintenance of organizational knowledge.

- c. **Content Management:** It automates the process that creates the web content and documentation in an organization.
- d. **Portals:** These are the organizational websites to aggregate multiple information for different work groups.
- e. **Learning:** It helps to customize training, mentoring and education software.
- f. **Scheduling and meeting tools:** It control the schedules and meetings through a pre-defined planning methods and notifications.

7. Conclusion

This paper is an outline of knowledge management theory and application. Various dimensions, approaches, strategies, motivation provided and technologies of knowledge management are described in order to avoid the unprecedented hurdles in common life and to make developmental process lively. Therefore, there is an urgent need to incorporate knowledge management strategies and theories in common processes of organisation. Today, there are various technologies available that help the system to be easy and smooth. If knowledge is managed in an efficient manner, it becomes easier to access and share facts, information and solutions any time and in any situation by the use of ICT.

Knowledge is managed by using Knowledge Management System (KMS) that can be document based, ontology based or artificial Intelligence based. KM approaches may enhance the quality dissemination of e-governance methods. It needs to replace the traditional skills and practices by technical and management skills. The author, hereby, draws the attention of government to establish a nationwide-knowledge-management portal to access, share and create knowledge for everyone.

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